

**METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND COMPARATIVE
METHODS. REQUIREMENTS FOR MODERN EDUCATORS. PROFESSIONAL-
PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE.**

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific perspective on the methods of teaching foreign languages, their comparative analysis, the requirements for modern teachers, and the issues of professional and pedagogical culture. Traditional and modern methods (grammar-translation, direct method, audio-lingual, communicative and task-based teaching) are compared. The need for teacher competencies, cultural sensitivity, reflexive practice and integration of technologies in the digital era is analyzed. Professional and pedagogical culture is interpreted as a set of motivational, cognitive, operational and value-based components. The article emphasizes the need for a synergistic approach to teaching foreign languages, the centrality of the learner and intercultural communication in the context of globalization. emphasizes the importance of developing competence.

Keywords: Methods of teaching foreign languages, comparative methodology, modern teacher competencies, professional- pedagogical culture, communicative teaching, task-based approach, digital integration, intercultural competence.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is constantly evolving under the influence of linguistic theory, psychology, and the changing needs of society. In the early stages, the grammar-translation method dominated, which was largely based on the experience of teaching classical languages. This method was based on text analysis, vocabulary memorization, and translation exercises, and gave priority to grammatical accuracy, but had serious shortcomings in the development of oral speech and real communication skills. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, a direct method emerged, based on the principles of natural language acquisition. This method advocated the use of only the target language in the learning process, inductive grammar learning, and the extensive use of visual and moving materials.

In the mid-20th century, the audio-lingual method became widespread under the influence of behavioral psychology and structural linguistics. This approach aimed to develop automatic responses through habit formation, repetition, dialogues, and patterned exercises. However, this method was criticized for its meaningless repetition and lack of attention to creative communication. Since the 1970s, the communicative approach (CLT) has brought about a paradigmatic change in language teaching. This method has focused on the functional use of language in real-life situations, negotiating meaning, role-playing, information exchange, and cultural adaptation. Task-based learning (TBL) is a communicative approach As a more advanced form of the approach, it proposes to master the language within the framework of realistic goal-oriented tasks. In this case, language forms are formed naturally, based on the communicative needs of the learner. Scientific research shows that TBL is more effective than traditional exercises in increasing long-term memory and motivation. At the same time, a comparative analysis of these methods shows that there is no universal "best" method in language teaching-

each method is effective in its own context. The most important thing is to use a synthesis approach that is adapted to the age, motivation, learning goals and learning environment of the learner.

In the digital era, foreign language teaching methods have reached a new level. It is no longer enough for a modern teacher to have only linguistic knowledge and pedagogical skills. He or she must work with digital tools (online platforms, artificial intelligence-based programs, virtual reality environments), design personalized learning paths, and implement flipped classrooms. classroom) and gamification elements. At the same time, in a culturally diverse environment, the teacher must have intercultural sensitivity, inclusiveness, and the ability to respect the cultural background of students.

Professional- pedagogical culture is considered an integrative indicator of a teacher's personal and professional development. It includes the following main components:

- motivational – internal interest in the profession and willingness to self-educate;
- cognitive – the ability to constantly acquire new knowledge and analyze modern research;
- operational-ability to adapt and apply various methods and technologies;
- value-based-principles of professional ethics, responsibility, and respect for the student.

In the context of teaching foreign languages, a teacher with a high level of professional and pedagogical culture develops in students not only language skills, but also cultural and social competencies necessary for successful communication in a global world. This process requires the teacher to constantly improve his/her work. It requires reflection, sharing experiences, and openness to innovation.

In conclusion, today, effective teaching of foreign languages requires a rational synthesis of traditional and modern methods, rational use of digital tools, and high professional and pedagogical culture. The teacher is not only a provider of knowledge, but also a person who prepares the student for global citizenship, serving as a bridge for intercultural communication. Future research should focus on hybrid learning models, the role of artificial intelligence in language teaching, and ensuring equal opportunities.

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